

Integrated climate forcing and air pollution reduction in urban systems (ICARUS): Ljubljana case study

Celovit pristop za zmanjševanje klimatskih sprememb in onesnaževanje zraka v urbanih sistemih (ICARUS): primer mesta Ljubljana

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ICARUS is an ongoing H2020 project that will develop innovative tools for urban impact assessment in support of air quality and climate change governance in the EU. The goal is to design and implement a set of win-win strategies to improve the air quality (AQ) and reduce the carbon footprint in European cities. The ICARUS methodology and toolkit will be applied in nine EU cities of variable size, socio-economic condition and history. Herein we present some preliminary results and activities for Ljubljana, Slovenia, which is one of the cities involved in the project.

In the frame of ICARUS project for Ljubljana city, spatially distributed activity–emission database was developed for year 2015 for the following twelve pollutants: BC, CH₄, CO, CO₂, N₂O, NH₃, NMVOC, NO_x, OC, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, SO₂ related to the following major emission relevant sectors: 1) public electricity and heat production, 2) industrial com-

bustion, 3) transport (Logar et al., 2017). The emission database will serve as an input for AQ (Air Quality) models that will in turn enable testing of various scenarios for the reduction of emissions based on analyses of feasible measures to be implemented.

Complying the common selection criteria, the following policies and measures have been selected for further analysis. The attention is mainly on the main pollution parameters, i.e. NO_x, CO, CO₂ and PM₁₀ which are related primarily to transport and household/building heating as well as energy use. In transport sector, the following measures are considered: increased share of walking, decreased use of personal cars, prohibition of heavy freight vehicles on the northern Ljubljana bypass, renovation of public passenger transport vehicle fleet (CNG, hybrid buses), utility vehicle fleet and city administration vehicle fleet and promotion of electromobility. Household heating and energy supply measures and policies include: increased utilization and expansion of district heating systems, increase in connecting facilities to the gas network, further encouragement of the replacement of existing combustion units with more means that are appropriate and increase in connecting facilities to the gas network (Tahir et al., 2011).

Social economic status (SES, e.g. gender, occupation, employment type, educational level, car ownership, education...) was evaluated for Ljubljana area in order to establish its relation with the air pollution situation. In the next steps physical-activity and air monitoring sensors will be used to evaluate exposure of citizens to air pollution in two upcoming sampling campaigns (summer and winter 2018). Along with the SES data, these results will serve as an input for agent-based modelling (ABM) (City Municipality of Ljubljana, 2013).

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